

MICROSTRUCTURE AND MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF 6061 AL ALLOY REINFORCED WITH SiC NANOPARTICLES PROCESSED BY EXTRUSION AND COLD ROLLING

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Abstract: A 6061 Al alloy composite reinforced with 15wt% SiC particles has been produced by powder processing routes followed by extrusion and cold rolling. The microstructure and mechanical properties were compared with the 6061 Al alloy produced by powder compaction followed by extrusion. Microstructural characterization and mechanical property tests have been carried out in as-extruded and as-rolled conditions. No interfacial reactions were promoted during the fabrication procedures. A significant realignment of SiC particles were obtained after cold rolling. The particle free bands in as-extruded sample have disappeared with further rolling passes, resulting in a more homogeneous distribution of SiC particles. The microhardness values of the 6061Al/SiC_p sample are much higher than those of the 6061Al sample. With increasing rolling reductions, the microhardness values of both the composite and 6061Al alloy increases until reaching a limit value. The three-point bending strength of as-rolled composite has surpassed the as-extruded composite by a significant amount.

Keywords: *metal matrix nanocomposites; powder metallurgy; microstructure; mechanical properties*

1 General introduction

During the past thirty years, the development of metal matrix composites (MMC) has been one of the prime innovations in materials. Early studies on MMCs mainly focused on the development of continuous fibre reinforced materials. However, high manufacturing costs coupled with high costs of the reinforcement fibres and complex fabrication routes have hindered their industrial applications and led to the development of particulate reinforced composites [1].

Particulate reinforced Al alloy composites are attractive materials for automotive and aerospace applications due to their lightweight, high modulus and strength and high wear resistance [2]. Many techniques have been developed to produce these kinds of composites. According to the different processing temperature, the processing methods can be loosely divided into two categories: liquid phase processing techniques such as casting and solid phase processing techniques including powder metallurgy routes [1]. After the primary fabrication methods, secondary processing techniques such as

extrusion, rolling or forging are necessary for consolidating the composites and decreasing their porosity [3].

Extrusion is a very effective step to improve the density and mechanical properties of MMCs. Cocen and Önel [4] studied as-cast and extruded Al alloy/SiC_p composites and found that with the same matrix and reinforcement volume fractions, the tensile strength values of the extruded composites were improved by ~40% compared with as-cast composites. Similar experimental results were also observed by Rahmani Fard and Akhlaghi [3] on A356/SiC_p composites and Tham et al. [5] on Al/SiC_p composites. Multiple explanations are given for the effect of the extrusion process on the composites' properties. First of all, the high temperature and pressure during extrusion is an effective way to break up the oxide layer on the surface of the powder particles, resulting in enhanced adhesion of the matrix-particle interfacial areas [6]. Secondly, extrusion can decrease porosity, refine particle size, break up particle agglomerations and lead to a more uniform distribution of reinforcement particles [7]. All these combined

factors result in a significant improvement on the mechanical properties of composites after extrusion. Appropriate processing parameters, such as extrusion ratio and extrusion temperature, need to be explored to obtain a fine microstructure and eliminate extrusion defects, such as particle cracking and microporosity.

Rolling is another secondary processing technique that allows obtaining metal matrix composites in flat shapes. However, compared with extrusion, few published papers have systematically studied the effect of cold rolling with high rolling reductions on microstructure and mechanical properties of composites. Sajjad Amirkhanlou et al. [8] compared 6061Al/SiC_p composite produced by compositing followed by cold rolling to different reductions and found out that the rolled specimens exhibited reduced porosity and a more uniform distribution of SiC particles in the matrix, resulting in a much higher tensile strength and elongation. In general, during cold rolling, the strength of the composites can increase significantly due to work hardening effects. In addition, porosity elimination and particle realignment can be achieved. However, severe damages such as cavitations, particle cracking and crack growth can easily happen since rolling involves high local strains being imposed really quickly, especially at low temperatures [9].

In the present work, 6061 Al alloy matrix composites reinforced with SiC nanoparticles have been produced by powder processing routes followed by extrusion and cold rolling. For comparison purposes, 6061 Al strips were also produced using the same extrusion and rolling conditions. Microstructural characterization, texture analysis and mechanical property tests have been carried out on as-extruded and as-rolled samples. The effect of extrusion and cold rolling on the overall properties of the composites has been analyzed.

2 Experimental procedure

6061 Al alloy reinforced with 15wt% SiC particles of an average particle size of 500nm billets were received from an industrial collaborator. The billets were produced by high energy ball milling followed by solid state compaction and HIPping. For comparison purposes, 6061 Al powder of an average size of 10 μ m was cold compacted with a load of 350KN. The 6061 Al alloy and composite billets were extruded at 375°C with an extrusion ratio of

6:1 to obtain strips with 6mm thickness. All the extruded strips were solution heat treated at 525°C for 3h followed by water quenching. The heat treated strips were then cold rolled with multiple rolling passes till the thickness of ~1mm was achieved.

Microstructural characterization was carried out on as-extruded and as-rolled samples by means of X-ray diffraction (XRD) and microscopy analysis. The samples for XRD analysis were polished down to P1200 SiC papers to obtain a flat and smooth surface. A Philips 1810 θ -2 θ diffractometer was used with the following scanning parameters: Cu-K α radiation, scanning angle 2 θ between 10-100°, step size 0.02°, voltage at 35kV and filament current of 50mA. A JEOL 6300 scanning electron microscope (SEM) was used for the microscopy analysis.

The crystallographic texture of as-extruded and as-rolled samples was measured on a Philips X'pert MRD system. All samples used for texture analysis were taken from the intermediate section of the strips. Four incomplete pole figures {1 1 1}, {2 0 0}, {2 2 0} and {3 1 1} were measured up to a maximum tilt angle of 85° by the Schulz back-reflection method using Cu-K α radiation. Orientation distribution functions (ODFs) were then calculated from the pole figures after background and defocusing corrections.

Mechanical properties of the as-extruded and as-rolled samples were analyzed by means of microhardness and three-point bending tests. Cross sections of the strips after each rolling pass were cut and mechanically polished to a mirror-like finish for microhardness testing using a load of 0.2Kg and a holding time of 20s. More than 20 measurements were made for each specimen. The flat bending samples were cut along the extrusion (ED) or rolling direction (RD) with dimension 12mm \times 1mm \times 1mm and then mechanically polished on every side down to P4000 SiC papers. The tests were performed in an Instron 3366 testing machine with a constant strain rate of 10⁻⁴s⁻¹. At least two tests were performed for each specimen.

3 Results and Discussions

3.1 XRD analysis

XRD analysis has been carried out on as-extruded and as-rolled 6061Al alloy and 6061Al/SiC_p

composite to identify the phases present during the manufacturing process. The diffractograms are shown in figure 1. For as-extruded 6061Al alloy, fcc-Al and intermetallic phase Mg_2Si were identified. After cold rolling, both Mg_2Si and $AlFeSi$ [10,11] phases were observed indicating that large plastic deformation might promote precipitation process.

For 6061Al/SiC_p composite, a previous work [12] have shown that SiC particles tend to react with Al matrix during the processing steps, forming Al_4C_3 and Si precipitates at the interface, which are detrimental to the overall mechanical properties of the composites. In the as-extruded composite, XRD analysis identified fcc-Al phase, 6H-SiC phase and the same intermetallic phases observed for the 6061Al alloy. No other phases were observed indicating that no interfacial reaction is detected by XRD. The X-ray diffractogram of the as-rolled composite did not show much difference compared with the diffractogram of the as-extruded composite, which indicates that the cold rolling process did not promote the interfacial reactions between Al matrix and SiC particles as it is observed in the limits of the XRD resolution.

In addition, it is observed from figure 1 that the relative intensities of each Al peaks have changed in as-extruded and as-rolled conditions. This is an indication that the Al grains have rotated to their preferred orientations during cold rolling, forming certain textures in as-rolled samples, which is discussed in detail in section 3.3.

3.2 Microstructure

Figure 2 shows the SEM images of as-received billet, as-extruded and cold rolled (down to 1mm) 6061Al/SiC_p composite. It can be seen from figure 2(a) that the SiC particles are not homogeneously distributed in the as-receive billet. There are some areas free of SiC particles (see arrows). After extrusion, those areas are observed as particle free bands with a width of 5-10 μ m along the extrusion direction (ED) (figure 2(b)). The banded structure can be reduced even disappear when increasing the extrusion ratio and/or the extrusion temperature according to literature [3,13]. In the present work, a low extrusion ratio and temperature has been used which led to an insufficient flow of the matrix alloy to obtain a homogeneous particle distribution. Besides, a small amount of porosity was observed after extrusion which was also due to extrusion conditions used.

During cold rolling, with increasing rolling reductions, the SiC particulate free zones became narrower and most of them disappeared after about 70% rolling reductions. Finally, a uniform distribution of SiC particles in the 6061 Al matrix can be observed in figure 2(c). Similar behaviours of the redistribution of particulate reinforcements during rolling were also observed elsewhere [14-16]. During cold rolling, cracks began to develop at the side of the strips and grew inside with more rolling passes, especially for the 6061Al/SiC_p composite sample. However, no cracks were found in the middle of the strips.

Careful observation of figure 2(c) also shows that the amount of porosity in the composite has largely decreased compared with as-extruded sample. It indicates that rolling can reduce the number of pores and improve interfacial bonding strength between 6061 Al matrix and SiC particles, since high pressure and metal flow during the rolling process can easily removed porosity and improve bonding cohesion increasing the relative density of the as-extruded composite.

Although the amount of porosity has reduced after rolling, a considerable amount of SiC particle cracking was formed during cold rolling as illustrated in the inset picture in figure 2(c). It is believed that the substantial increase in rolling pressure is the reason for such cracking in the SiC particles. The brittle SiC particles will fracture once the stress concentration reaches the fracture strength of the particles. Especially for relatively larger particles, they are more likely to fracture than smaller sized particles since they endure higher stress concentrations and have a higher possibility of containing flaws [17].

3.3 Texture analysis

The crystallographic texture of Al alloys and their composites during extrusion and rolling has long been studied by many researchers since anisotropy is very important to the overall mechanical properties [18].

ODFs of 6061Al alloy and 6061Al/SiC_p composite in as-extruded and as-rolled conditions are shown in figure 3 to study the texture evolution during extrusion and rolling. From figure 3(a) and 3(b), it can be seen that after extrusion into strips and solution heat treatment, the 6061Al alloy has a strong orientation near S component ($\varphi_1=65$, $\Phi=35$,

$\phi_2=65$). After cold rolling, the texture can be described by a β fibre which runs from Brass component ($\phi_1=35$, $\Phi=45$, $\phi_2=90$) to Copper component ($\phi_1=90$, $\Phi=35$, $\phi_2=45$) through S component, which is the typical fibre texture after cold rolling of fcc metals [19]. For 6061Al/SiC_p composite (shown in figure 3(c) and 3(d)), after extrusion and heat treatment, the sample has a moderate strong texture component near S. After cold rolling, instead of getting sharper textures like 6061Al alloy, the texture of the composite sample is quite random with a bit higher intensities near S. All these features were more clearly shown in figure 4 which depicts the intensities along β orientation lines.

Compared with 6061Al alloy, the 6061Al/SiC_p composite has weaker texture components in both as-extruded and as-rolled condition due to the additions of non-deformable SiC reinforcement. For 6061Al alloy, the Al grains rotate and elongate along the extrusion or rolling direction, hence, a strong plane strain deformation texture is developed. For 6061Al/SiC_p composite, due to the formation of deformation zones around the SiC particles where very high density of dislocation and strong lattice rotations are being built up, grain rotations will be restricted to some extent [20,21]. As a result, the Al grains near SiC particles cannot rotate to the preferred orientation like the rest of the matrix, resulting in weaker texture components.

In general, the texture intensities become stronger with increasing cold rolling reductions, like is observed for the 6061Al alloy. In the case of 6061Al/SiC_p composite, the orientations of Al grains become weaker and randomized with further rolling reductions. This is closely related with the microstructure change in as-extruded and as-rolled conditions. As discussed in section 3.2, the as-extruded 6061Al/SiC_p composite has particle free bands and particle rich zones. The particle free bands are the areas with typical deformation textures since they are far away from SiC particles. The Al orientations in particle rich zones, however, due to the deformation zones around SiC particles, are randomized. During cold rolling, the particle free bands become narrower and a homogeneous distribution of SiC particles was achieved in the final rolled sample. The disappearance of particle free bands lead to the random texture in as-rolled sample since the Al grains have no preferred orientations when it is around the SiC particles.

3.4 Microhardness

Microhardness is a useful method for quickly allowing judgment of a material's performance, as it is closely related to the yield stress. Microhardness data on as-extruded and cold rolled specimens after each rolling pass was plotted as a function of the rolling strain in figure 5. It shows that the microhardness of both samples increase with increasing strains due to work hardening up to a maximum limit value. The microhardness values of 6061Al/SiC_p composite sample have increased about 33%, from 120 μ HV₂₀₀ in as-extruded state to 160 μ HV₂₀₀ after cold rolling at a true strain of 3.3. For 6061Al sample, the microhardness values increased 100%, from 60 μ HV₂₀₀ at the as-extruded state to 120 μ HV₂₀₀ after cold rolling at a true strain of 3.6. The 6061Al alloy has a larger work hardening capacity than the 6061Al/SiC_p composite. All of the values for the 6061Al/SiC_p sample are much higher than those of the 6061Al sample indicating effective strengthening from the SiC particles.

The empirical power-law relationship developed by Holloman [22] was used to describe the microhardness-strain curves:

$$\mu HV = \mu HV_0 + K \cdot (\varepsilon - \varepsilon_0)^m \quad (1)$$

where μ HV is the microhardness as a function of rolling strain, ε , μ HV₀ is the initial microhardness value in as-extruded condition, K and m are fitting parameters dependent on the material and the testing temperature and ε_0 is the initial strain value after extrusion, which equals to 1.77 in the present work.

Figure 5 also shows the fitted lines for both specimens based on eq. 1. It is obvious that the fitted lines are in good agreement with the experimental data. Material constants K and m are obtained from the curve fittings and work hardening rates $d\mu HV/d\varepsilon$

$$d\mu HV/d\varepsilon = K \cdot m \cdot (\varepsilon - \varepsilon_0)^{m-1} \quad (2)$$

are computed and plotted in figure 6 as a function of true strain.

From figure 6, it is clear that the initial work hardening rate is high and then decreases with increasing strains for both materials. The work hardening rate is governed by dislocation accumulations and the dynamic recovery rate. At the beginning of deformation, the number of

dislocations increases as deformation proceeds. Dislocations on different slip systems intersect and the intersections block the dislocations from further motion, causing rapid work hardening rate [23]. Then at a certain point, cross slip or climb of dislocations is launched, causing dislocations with opposite signs to meet and annihilate, a lowering work hardening abilities is developed. With further deformations, a balance between dislocation generation and annihilation is created where no more hardening happens and a stress limit is reached [24].

For 6061Al alloy, in solid solution state, solute atoms have a pinning effect to the gliding dislocations and can effectively reduce the dynamic recovery rate, leading to high work hardening capabilities. For Al alloy composites, some researchers [25] found that smaller size particles will increase the work hardening of composites. This conclusion is in contradiction with figure 6 which shows a lower work hardening rate for 6061Al/SiC_p composite than for 6061Al alloy. It is believed that the large amount of particle cracking in the composite system is the reason for this contradiction. Particle cracking and the subsequent development of microvoids near the fractured particles can caused localised strain softening and lead to a decrease in the overall work hardening rate [26]. Similar results were also observed recently by M. Soliman et al. [27] who found that the work hardening rate for 7108Al reinforced with 20vol.% of SiC particles is lower than the matrix itself.

3.5 Bending properties

Bending test is normally required at industry to evaluate sheet formability and anisotropy of produced sheet [28]. Figure 7 shows the schematic illustrations for the three-point bending tests with sample orientations (ND: normal direction; ED: extrusion direction; RD: rolling direction). Based on the Force-Displacement curves from the three-point bending tests, flexural stress (σ) and flexural strain (ϵ) were calculated by Eq. 3 and Eq. 4:

$$\sigma = (3 * P * L)/(2 * w * t^2) \quad (3)$$

$$\epsilon = (6 * t * D)/L^2 \quad (4)$$

Where, P is the applied load at the centre of the beam, L is the span length, w is the width of the specimen, t is the thickness of the specimen and D is the displacement of the beam at the centre, respectively [28]. None of the specimens have

fractured during the tests since the equipment limitation has been reached.

The calculated flexural stress–flexural strain curves for different specimens were plotted in figure 8 and the yield stress values were summarized in Table 1. Compared to 6061Al alloy specimens, the 6061Al/SiC_p composite has much higher yield strength. The yield strength of as-extruded and as-rolled 6061Al/SiC_p composite has increased by 105% and 31% compared with as-extruded and as-rolled 6061Al alloy, respectively, indicating effective strengthening from SiC reinforcements. Due to the increasing amount of SiC particle cracking during cold rolling, the extent of increase in yield strength has declined compared with as-extruded specimens. In addition, texture analysis suggests that with further rolling passes, the 6061Al/SiC_p composite has no preferred orientations while the 6061Al alloy has developed a sharp β fibre texture, causing a reduced amount of texture strengthening for as-rolled 6061Al/SiC_p composite when compared to as-rolled 6061Al alloy.

Furthermore, for 6061Al alloy and 6061Al/SiC_p composite, the yield strength of as-rolled specimens has increased by 100% and 28% compared with as-extruded specimens, respectively. It is suggested that the amount of dislocation densities brought by during cold rolling is the main reason for the improved yield strength.

4 Conclusions

6061 Al alloy reinforced with SiC nanoparticles has been produced by powder processing routes followed by extrusion and cold rolling.

The as-extruded and as-rolled 6061Al/SiC_p composite samples both have fcc-Al phase, 6H-SiC phase and a minor fractions of other intermetallic phases. No interfacial reaction phases were identified by XRD and microscopy analysis, indicating no evidence of interfacial reactions during manufacture procedures and the following extrusion and rolling process.

A significant redistribution of SiC particles was obtained during cold rolling. Particle free bands in as-extruded condition disappeared after ~70% of cold rolling reduction, resulting in a homogeneous distribution of SiC particles within 6061Al matrix. Porosity was also reduced till disappeared after cold rolling. Meanwhile, substantial amounts of SiC

particle fracture were formed in rolling process, preferably in larger sized particles.

The 6061Al alloy develops a typical β fibre texture during cold rolling while the 6061Al/SiC_p composite has randomized Al grain orientations after rolling due to the presence of non-deformable SiC particles, causing the formation of deformation zones around the particles.

Microhardness values of 6061Al alloy and 6061Al/SiC_p composite increase with increasing rolling strains up to a limit value. Both materials have a relatively high initial work hardening rate and then decrease rapidly with increasing rolling strains. Compared with 6061Al alloy, 6061Al/SiC_p composite has a lower work hardening rate due to the microstructure imperfections.

The flexural yield strength from three-point bending tests show improved strength of 105% for 6061Al/SiC_p composite compared with 6061Al alloy in as-extruded condition. Despite the increasing amount of SiC particle cracking during cold rolling, the as-rolled specimens still exhibit improved strength respect to the as-extruded specimens.

Overall, the cold rolling process on 6061Al/SiC_p nanocomposite improves homogeneity of the microstructure and increases the strength considerably. Also, it does not introduce anisotropy as crystallographic texture in Al alloy matrix is quite random.

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Fig. 1. X-ray diffractograms of the as-extruded and as-rolled 6061Al alloy and 6061Al/SiC_p composite

Fig. 2. SEM images of: (a) as-received 6061Al/SiC_p composite; (b) as-extruded 6061Al/SiC_p composite; (c) as-rolled 6061Al/SiC_p composite after ~77% reduction. (ED: Extrusion direction; RD: Rolling direction). Arrows indicate particle free areas. Inset shows a cracked particle

Fig. 3. ODFs of as-extruded and as-rolled 6061Al alloy and 6061Al/SiC_p composite in three ϕ_2 sections, (a): As-extruded 6061Al alloy; (b): As-rolled 6061Al alloy; (c): As-extruded 6061Al/SiC_p composite; (d): As-rolled 6061Al/SiC_p composite

Fig. 4. β fibre intensities of the Al matrix in the as-extruded and as-rolled 6061Al alloy and 6061Al/SiC_p composite

Fig. 5. Microhardness of cold rolled 6061Al alloy and 6061Al/SiC_p composite samples as a function of the rolling strain and microhardness fitted lines based on eq. 1

Fig. 6. Work hardening rates for cold rolled 6061Al and 6061Al/SiC_p specimens as a function of true strain

Fig. 7. Schematic illustration for the three-point bending tests (ED: Extrusion direction; RD: Rolling direction; ND: Normal direction)

Fig. 8. Three-point bending curves for as-extruded and cold rolled 6061Al alloy and 6061Al/SiC_p composite samples. Cold rolled samples were tested under a condition of true strain of 3.6 and 3.3 for the alloys and the composite respectively.

Specimen	Condition	Stress at yield (MPa)
6061Al	As-extruded	235±17
	As-rolled	471±21
6061Al/SiC _p	As-extruded	482±28
	As-rolled	616±15

Table 1. Bending properties of 6061Al alloy and 6061Al/SiC_p composite in as-extruded and cold rolled conditions

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